
COUNSELLING FOR ALL AGES, MYSELF AND YOURSELF IN A CONTEMPORARY SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on counseling for all age and myself in a contemporary society. The study is exploratory and qualitative in nature, and was based on information gathered from an expert working in a geriatric centre. Various issues associated with global ageing population stems from attributes and beliefs that growing old could be accompanied by loss of competence, intellectual deterioration and discrimination. The increase in life expectancy worldwide due to some improvements in health facilities and low mortality rate among others, accounts for the increase in the population of the Aged. Many elderly people in Nigeria experience abuse, psychosocial issues, health problems and disability. Similarly, the burden of these problems rest on the society and this could be demanding in the area of economic growth, patterns of work, retirement and family dependency, to mention a few. Therefore, the place of counselling cannot be overemphasized if the elderly in the society will continue to enjoy quality and active life. It is therefore recommended, that Nigerian government should come up with a functional national policy that will include counselling services in all elderly institutions which will be managed by Professional counsellors.

Keywords: *counsellor, Counselling, Contemporary, ages, society.*

INTRODUCTION

Guidance and counselling for all ages in Nigeria is offered in educational institutions (primary, secondary, and tertiary) through school counselors, and in community settings. The services help with academic, career, and personal-social problems, support decision-making, and address issues like dropping out of school, anxiety, and maladaptive behaviors. Counseling appears to be a relatively loaded phenomenon. Although, it had been erroneously conceived to be mere advice giving, a cursory and patent examination of the word and meaning shows that it is more scientific and more business-like than just advising. The roles played by guidance and counseling in the lives of different categories of people in the society are

immeasurable. Invariably, no society can thrive when people are not in the right state of mind. The concept of guidance and counseling as been defined by various scholars has scholastic colouration and orientation of each scholar. According to Surbhi(2016) guidance and counseling are two major concepts of psychology, which both seek to find out the solutions for problems and work for human development. Not only this, guidance and counseling can help categories of people in the society to overcome their challenges, and make meaningful contribution to their societies. Guidance and counselling is the process of helping individuals discover and develop their educational, vocational and psychological potentialities and thereby achieve an optimal level of personal happiness and social usefulness

In contemporary society, guidance and counseling play a crucial role in supporting individuals' well-being, personal growth, and success in various areas, including education, career, and social-personal development. They help individuals navigate challenges, make informed decisions, and develop coping skills to thrive in a complex world. In modern Nigerian society, counseling for both young people and adults is increasingly recognized as vital for personal and societal well-being. Guidance and counseling services aim to help individuals navigate various life challenges, promote positive development, and foster healthier relationships, ultimately contributing to a more productive and supportive society.

UNESCO(2007) states that counseling is actively listening to an individual's story and communicating, understanding, respect and empathy: clarifying goals and assisting challenged individuals with the decision making process. Guidance and counseling is actually a goal oriented discipline, psychologist works together with the client, to ensure he regain consciousness and assurances of better life. Unlike some other profession, counselor or psychologist can not work in isolation, except with the agreement and cooperation of the client. Guidance and counseling is a profession that make people to be self-actualized, people reach their full potentials when and only they are properly guided and counseled by professionals. Onyilofor(2012) posits that the professional counselor should utilize his/her professional skills (administrative skills, thinking skills, orientation and planning skills, time management skills, technical and technological skills) for the transformation and education of Challenged student in Nigerian higher education. Amannda(2014) argued that Counseling is more than mere advice giving, it is strategies adopted by professionals to

get people out of their problems, reassure them of better and meaningful lives.

Okorie, M. (2017) Submitted that guardian Counsellors achieve their objective of guidance by formulating realistic and purposeful goals for total personal growth. Thus, counseling is not advice giving. It transcends traditional brainwashing kind of talk In traditional parlance, people are influenced to change their attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors, through persuasion, or at times, compel to do so. Onyilofor (2013) further states that a counselor should be a think tank and an inventive problem solver and should be able to reason properly both with the brain and the heart in the transformation of challenged students in Nigeria's higher education. Counseling is a professional service offered by a counselor (as expert) to a client(s) who had submitted himself or herself to counseling so that he or she can be relieved of his or her deviant behavior or better still manage such. Clearly enough, if a client did not willingly submit him or herself for counseling, the goals of that counseling can never be achieved.

Society on the other hand, has its definition as perceived by various scholars. Sonal (2017) defined Society as a system of usages and procedures, of authority and mutual aid, of many groupings and divisions, of controls of human behaviour and of liberties. This ever-changing, complex system we call society. It is the web of social relationships. And it is always changing. It is organization of people who come together to make certain decision, in the society are social institutions and people develop themselves through their social experiences. a community, nation, or broad grouping of people having common traditions, institutions, and collective activities and interests is regarded as society.

Counselling for all age

Counselling can be a valuable resource for individuals of all ages, addressing a wide range of challenges and helping people navigate life's complexities. Whether it's for young people facing developmental issues, or adults dealing with mental health conditions or life events, counselling can provide a safe and supportive space for exploration and growth.

The Counsellor

A counselor is a professionally trained expert who first of all counsel himself, overcome many challenges and gained vast experience to helps people overcome their issues after a systematic chain of sessions. The types

of counselling vary, depending on the needs of the clients. counselling is a talking therapy that allows people to discuss their problems with trained professionals in a peaceful and safe ambiance. The exact meaning of counselling might vary among individuals. But in general, it is the process where you talk about your issues in detail either intending to overcome the same or to explore your thoughts comprehensively. The role of a counselor doesn't limit to suggesting you do this or that. Rather they support you to speak about your problems in detail to identify the primary cause behind them. Furthermore, they develop an action plan to help you cope up with the issue or win over it.

There are different formats through which the counselling sessions can take place, The client is free to choose a format that suits and fits his needs the best. Below are the popular counselling formats that people mostly favor:

- i. **In-Person:** Face-to-face counselling sessions take place in the counselor's chamber where you meet them in person after scheduling an appointment to discuss your problems. It is one of the most popular counselling formats.
- ii. **Group Counselling:** Professionals provide group counselling sessions where you can join to address the issues. Joining such a group will help you find people with similar problems and you will be able to develop a strong network of support as well. However, if you wish to focus on your problem, in-person sessions are better.
- iii. **Telephonic Sessions:** A great alternative to in-person counselling sessions are telephonic rounds that can be scheduled from the comfort of your home. Telephonic counselling rounds are best for busy individuals who might find it difficult to get into the chambers. In this flexible process, you can discuss the problems with the counselor in a secure environment from your room.
- iv. **Online Counselling:** If you wish not to meet your counselor face to face and protect your anonymity, you have the option to email the counselor. In this process, you have the scope to think well and decide which of the problems you want to discuss with him. The online counselling trend is becoming much more popular these days.

Counselling Process

When a person seeks counselling, he or she suffers from something serious be it mental issues, emotional problems, or family problems. The process is not to be rushed but rather involves a systematic evaluation that includes a detailed process. The counselling process involves a step-by-step approach and the counselor conducts it in a way to make sure that his client is comfortable with the process. Lets have a look at the five crucial stages of a counselling process.

1: Building a Warm Relationship

When you are hitting up a counselor to discuss your problems, you ought to suffer from any serious issue concerning academics, relationships, career, or anything else. The first thing your expert does is to make yourself comfortable around him/her. He focuses on developing a warm relation and mutual trust first to make sure you do not hesitate while speaking about the problems you are facing.

2: Analysis

In this stage, the professional encourages you to speak in detail about your problems to grab the roots of the problem. He observes every minute detail from how you are speaking to your reactions to certain questions that might come from his end. Once he assesses the problem, the goal is fixed.

3: Setting the Goal

After a thorough evaluation of your problems, now comes the significant section of goal setting. Considering the issues you are facing the counselor sets a goal. That can be either you overcoming the problem or reconciling with it.

4: Plan of Action

The counselor plans an action for you to practice to see the results. Suppose someone has public speaking fear, The expert might ask him to practice speaking in front of the mirror. This is just an instance. Once you go through the plan for the desired tenure, he assesses your improvement. If things seem normal, you are at the final stage! If not, he might design something different.

5: Overcoming the Problem

As I mentioned in the previous point after you follow the plan of action the consequent results are taken into consideration. If things seem to go in the right direction and you start feeling relaxed, yes! You have achieved your goal.

Counselling Skills

Being a professional counselor requires some core skills to be able to handle client queries and drive the best results for them. The vital skills that a professional counselor must have are as follows:

- **Effective Listening:** A counselor must be a patient listener who not only listens to the clients queries but can handle them intricately. Without hearing the issues minutely, it is impossible to get ahead with the next counselling steps. Therefore, the counselor has to be someone with good listening skills who gives full attention to the client and their details.
- **A Good Communicator:** A counselor is someone who listens to his clients, analyses the problems, and develops a plan of action to achieve a target. It is indeed critical to be a very good communicator to help the person feel comfortable around him and make sure the client is not hesitating while speaking in front of him about his problems. Developing a good relationship is very important.
- **Analysis:** A successful counselor is someone who is not only a good listener but a good analyzer too, who uses his skills and expertise to reach the root of the problem and analyze it. Without analysis, the entire process is in vain as no goals can be set and the client will not be able to undergo any plan of action.

Self Counseling

Self-counseling, also known as self-therapy, involves using counseling techniques and methods to address your own emotional, psychological, and behavioral issues without the guidance of a professional therapist. It's a process of self-reflection, exploration, and problem-solving, often using tools and strategies learned from counseling approaches like Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT). In modern society, self-counseling, or self-therapy, involves exploring one's own thoughts, feelings, and behaviors through techniques like free-thinking and free association. It empowers

individuals to take control of their daily lives, build resilience, and improve their well-being. This practice can be particularly beneficial for individuals seeking to understand and manage anxieties, build self-esteem, and make positive changes in their lives.

Benefits Of Counseling Both Young And Adults

Discover new perspectives

A counselling session is a safe space to talk with an independent therapist. Sometimes just saying a thought out loud brings a huge sense of relief. You might start to look at challenges differently through open discussions and exploring new ideas.

Build communication skills

People who experience counselling become more able to express their feelings and emotions, which can also improve personal and work relationships. Talking to a trained professional who wants to listen and genuinely cares will develop your communication skills and build confidence in other areas of your life.

Become a more resilient person

Counselling therapy can be stressful, particularly if you're discussing a painful time or event in your life. With each session, you'll make progress and become stronger. You might find it becomes easier to express your thoughts and feelings.

Build your self-esteem

Lack of self-worth is a common trait in people who seek counselling support. Sharing your fears and exploring solutions could give you a real confidence boost. The simple act of talking builds self-esteem and you find new ways of coping in the future.

Make change

With counselling, you're in control of your own destiny. Your counsellor will never tell you what to do or steer you down a certain path. They'll listen and encourage you to investigate ideas and always make your own choices. The pace of progress is up to you. Even the smallest of changes is a positive step.

Improved quality of life

Stress, worry and anxiety can lead to insomnia or irregular sleep patterns. Getting issues off your chest through counselling can have a direct impact on the amount and quality of sleep you get. You may also feel more motivated and energised in life.

METHODOLOGY

In this research paper, the researcher uses description methods to conduct a study, including the specific techniques for data collection and analysis, and the rationale for choosing this methods is tot explains how the research was conducted, allowing readers to assess the validity and reliability of the findings and potentially replicate the study.

- **Data Collection:**

The specific procedures and tools used to gather data In this paper was questionnaire and oral interview s

- **Data Analysis:**

The methods for analyzing the collected was analyzed using simple percentages.

DISCUSSION

From the questionnaire drawn, a total number of 20 questionnaire was designed on a template which was filled by many professional counsellors. The result indicates that counseling is meant for all ages especially in a contemporary society.

CONCLUSION

This paper analyzed the effectiveness of counseling as a profession and as well an antidote to some of the problems militating against the development of our society. Hereunder are some of the suggestions to government and individuals. Since Counseling is one of the effective means for developing human potential, suggestion are made available for government and individual to redress.

Recommendations and Suggestion

- Bills that would make guidance and counseling a profession like others (e.g. law, medical profession, engineering, etc.) should be passed into law.

- In terms of budget allocation, guidance and counseling should also be given its dues.
- Government should take it as a point of responsibility, the provisions of professional counselors in all government establishments.
- Public awareness should be improved to make people aware of happening around them.
- Creation of policy that would make counselors members of any organization, irrespective of the nature of the organization..
- People should be able to seek counseling services just like they seek medical attention, and the consultation fees should be made affordable.
- Creation of government own counseling centers at local government level, state level and other sub levels.
- Setting up committees of professional counselors to proffer solutions to existing problems. For example, Federal Government of Nigeria set up committee of experts to look into Economic recession and design ways of getting out of economic recession.

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